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Development of Some Cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.] Accessions for Tolerance to Drought Stress

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Development of Some Cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.] Accessions for Tolerance to Drought Stress

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted in Nigeria at the screen house of International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Kano Station, during 2012 and 2014 growing seasons to develop Cowpea genotypes that are tolerant to drought stress with a view to solving the problem of climate change faced by the Cowpea farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa where annual rainfall is not stable. Based on the outcome of this study it was observed that breeding programme carried out with IT07K-322-40 which is a highly susceptible variety was used in both forward and reciprocal crosses and all the crosses involving it proved to be drought tolerant. This indicates that the gene for drought tolerance is highly heritable, response of F₁ progenies to drought stress revealed that, out of the ten (10) successful F₁ progenies evaluated (Table 1), five (5) were found to be drought tolerant, also four (4) were found to be drought susceptible and the remaining one which is IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40 was found to be intermediate. Backcross progenies indicate that out of the ten (10) successful backcross progenies tested for drought stress (percentage wilting and recovery), a total of seven (7) cowpea genotypes were found to be drought tolerant and two (2) others were rated drought susceptible (IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4 and (IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13, the remaining one was rated as intermediate (IT07K-291-92 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13. The result of the backcross progenies indicated that out of the total, ten (10) successful backcross progenies tested for drought stress, a total of seven (7) cowpea genotypes were found to be drought tolerant, two (2) others (IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4 and (IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13 were rated drought susceptible and the remaining one (IT07K-291-92 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13 was rated as intermediate which indicates that among all the methods of breeding carried out, the result of tolerance supersedes other methods.

Keywords: Backcross, F₁ progenies, Kano, Cowpea varieties, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.] is one of the most important food and forage legumes in the semi-arid tropics that includes parts of Asia, Africa, Southern Europe, Southern United States, and Central and South America (Singh 2005; Timko et al. 2007a). It is grown extensively in the low lands and mid-altitude regions of Africa (particularly in the dry savanna) sometimes as sole crop but more often intercropped with cereals such as sorghum or millet (Agbogidi, 2010a). Cowpea fixes atmospheric nitrogen through symbiosis with nodule bacteria (Shiringani and Shimeles, 2011). It does well and most popular in the semi-arid of the tropics where other food legumes do not perform well (Sankie et al., 2012).

Cowpea is of major importance to the livelihoods of millions of relatively poor people in less developed countries of the tropics (FAO, 2002). Among the legumes, cowpea is the most extensively grown, distributed and traded food crop consumed, accounting for more than 50% (Philips and McWalters, 1991; Ogbo, 2009; Agbogidi, 2010a). Many researchers including Adaji et al. (2007) and Adeniji (2007) have showed that daily consumption of 100–135 gm of dry beans reduces serum cholesterol level by 20% thereby, reducing the risk for coronary heart diseases by 40% (Anderson, 1985; Ofuya, 1993). Besides its health related benefits, beans are inexpensive, considerably cheaper than rice or any other dietary fibre type (Ayenlere et al., 2012). World production of cowpea was estimated to be 2.27 million tons of which Nigeria produces about 850,000 tonnes (FAO, 2002; Adaji et al., 2007).

It is an extremely resilient crop and cultivated under some of the most extreme agricultural conditions in the world (Owolade et al., 2006; Muoneke et al., 2012). Compared to other legumes, cowpea is known to have good adaptation to high temperatures and resistance to drought stress (Hall et al. 2002; Hall 2004). Drought affects nearly all the plant growth processes; however, the stress response depends upon the intensity, rate and duration of exposure and the stage of crop growth (Brar et al., 1990). The results may be wilting, cessation of growth, or even death of the plant or plant parts (Blum, 2004). Therefore, genetic enhancement of cowpea for drought tolerance by incorporating drought tolerance into early maturing cowpea lines represents the best and

most cost-effective method for ensuring sustainable and improved crop yield in variable and changing climates. Unstable rainfall in the early cropping season seems to be the pattern in the sub-region. There is also a rationale for incorporating tolerance to terminal drought, which is becoming more frequent in the sub-region due to reduction in the duration of the rainy season.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of plant materials:

Twenty three improved varieties of cowpea: IT07K-243-1-10, IT07K-298-15, IT07K-299-6, IT07K-322-40, IT06K-111, IT03K-378-4, IT07K-293-3, IT07K-313-41, IT04K-227-4, IT07K-291-92, IT07K-292-10, IT07K-297-13, IT07K-318-2, IT06K-270, IT07K-187-55, IT07K-244-1-1, IT04K-267-8, IT06K-275, IT97K-568-19, IT97K-461-4 and three local varieties DAN-ILA, KANANNADO and ALOKA were sourced from the Breeding unit of IITA, Kano station, Nigeria.

Breeding and development of new accessions

This method was performed using plastic pots measuring 250mm (both diameter and depth of about 10 to 20 cm, filled with 600g to 10 kg of soil) mixed with cured cow dung at a ratio of nine to one (9:1) part respectively and arranged on shelves in the screen house as described by (Matsui and Singh 2003). The pots were watered for two days before planting; The selected tolerant and susceptible varieties were then sown directly in pots at a depth of 1cm to 1.5cm in the pots at four (4) seeds per pot and a distance 9cm from each other within the pot (Ehlers et al. 2002a; Singh et al. 2002; Hall et al. 2003; Singh 2005; Timko et al. 2007a). After germination the plants were thinned to two (2) plants per pot and allowed to grow up to flowering stage in a screen house, one tolerant variety was crossed with one susceptible variety and the F_1 seeds were collected and kept in a white labelled envelope. F_1 seeds were planted along with parental varieties and crosses were made between them to obtain Backcross seeds while F_2 seeds were obtained by allowing F_1 plants to self-pollinate. The F_1 , backcross and F_2 populations were raised in the screen house and evaluated for drought tolerance as described above.

RESULTS

The response of F_1 progenies to drought stress revealed that, out of the ten (10) successful F_1 progenies evaluated (Table 1) five (5) were found to be drought tolerant, including Aloka x IT07K-322-40 with 22%, IT07K-322-40 x Aloka with 13%, IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4 with 17%, IT07K-291-92 x Aloka 25%, and IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4 also with 25%. Also four (4) were found to be drought susceptible which include IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40, IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13, IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92 and IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-297-13, and the remaining one which is IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40 was found to be intermediate i.e. neither tolerant nor susceptible to drought stress.

The result of the backcross progenies is presented in (Table 2 and 3). Out of the total ten (10) successful backcross progenies tested for drought stress (percentage wilting and recovery), a total of seven (7) cowpea genotypes were found to be drought tolerant and they include (Aloka x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-322-40 with 29%, (IT07K-322-40 x Aloka) x Aloka with 11%, (IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-322-40 with 25%, (IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-322-40 with 13%, (IT07K-291-92 x Aloka) x Aloka with 33%, (IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92) x IT07K-291-92 with 29% and (IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4 with 20%. Two (2) others were rated drought susceptible and they include (IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4 with 86% and (IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13 with 75%. The remaining one was rated as intermediate (IT07K-291-92 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13 with 50%, being neither tolerant nor susceptible to drought stress. Similarly F_2 progenies and their tolerance status indicates that out of the ten (10) F_2 progenies tested six (6) were found to be tolerant to drought and they include Aloka x IT07K-322-40 with 13%, IT07K-322-40 x Aloka with 22%, IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40 with 14%, IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4 with 20%, IT07K-291-92 x Aloka 25%, and IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4 with 14%. Whereas two (2) were found to be susceptible to drought stress and these include IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13 with 100% and IT07K-291-92 x IT07K-297-13 having 75%. Also, the remaining two (2) which include IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40 with 56% and IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92 with 50% prove to be intermediate i.e. neither tolerance nor susceptible (Table 4 and 5).

Table 1: Percentage wilting of F₁ cowpea genotypes at different days of drought imposition

Cowpea varieties	No. of plant stands	No. of wilted plants during drought stress				
		D8	D10	D12	D14	D15
Aloka x IT07K-322-40	09	00	00	00	22	22
IT07K-322-40 x Aloka	08	00	00	00	00	13
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40	04	00	00	25	50	50
IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4	06	00	00	00	17	17
IT07K-297-13 X IT07K-322-40	02	00	100	100	100	100
IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13	06	00	00	50	67	83
IT07K-291-92 x Aloka	04	00	00	25	25	25
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92	09	00	22	56	78	89
IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4	08	00	00	13	13	25

Table 2: Percentage recovery of F₁ Cowpea genotypes at different days after water restoration

Cowpea varieties	No. of plant Stands	No. of recovered plants during drought stress			
		D4	D6	D8	D10
Aloka x IT07K-322-40	09	11	44	44	67
IT07K-322-40 x Aloka	08	25	63	75	75
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40	04	00	00	25	50
IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4	06	00	33	50	67
IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40	02	00	00	00	00
IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13	06	00	00	17	17
IT07K-291-92 x Aloka	04	00	25	75	75
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92	09	00	00	11	22
IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4	08	38	50	75	88
IT07K-291-92 x IT07K-297-13	03	00	00	00	00

Table 3: Percentage wilting of Backcross progenies of cowpea at different days of drought imposition

Cowpea varieties	No. Of plant Stands	No. Of wilted plants during drought stress				
		D8	D10	D12	D14	D15
(Aloka x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-322-40	07	00	00	14	29	29
(IT07K-322-40 x Aloka) x Aloka	09	00	00	00	11	11
(IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-32240	08	00	00	13	25	25
(IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4	07	00	57	71	86	86
(IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-322-40	08	00	00	13	13	13
(IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13	08	00	25	63	75	75
(IT07K-291-92 x Aloka) x Aloka	09	00	00	22	22	33
(IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92) x IT07K-291-92	07	00	00	14	29	29
(IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4	05	00	00	00	00	20

Table 4: Percentage recovery of Backcross progenies of cowpea at different days after water restoration

Cowpea varieties	No. of plant stands	No. of recovered plants during drought stress			
		D4	D6	D8	D10
(Aloka x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-322-40	07	43	71	86	86
(IT07K-322-40 x Aloka) x Aloka	09	22	44	56	78
(IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-32240	08	00	25	63	75
(IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4	07	00	00	14	29
(IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40) x IT07K-322-40	08	25	63	75	88
(IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K-297-13	08	00	00	00	25
(IT07K-291-92 x Aloka) x Aloka	09	22	33	67	78
(IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92) x IT07K-291-92	07	00	29	57	71
(IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4) x IT03K-378-4	05	00	20	60	60
(IT07K-291-92 x IT07K-297-13) x IT07K297-13	06	00	00	50	50

Table 5: Percentage wilting of F₂ progenies of cowpea that show various degree of response at different days during drought stress imposition

Cowpea varieties	No. of plant stands	No. of wilted plants during drought stress				
		D8	D10	D12	D14	D15
Aloka x IT07K-322-40	08	00	00	13	13	13
IT07K-322-40 x Aloka	09	00	11	11	22	22
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40	07	00	00	00	00	14
IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4	05	00	00	20	20	20
IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40	09	00	11	33	56	56
IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13	08	38	63	88	100	100
IT07K-291-92 x Aloka	08	00	00	13	13	25
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92	06	00	00	17	33	50
IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4	07	00	00	00	00	14

Table 6: Percentage recovery of F₂ progenies of cowpea that show various degree of response to drought at different days after water restoration.

Cowpea varieties	No. of plant stands	No. of recovered plants during drought stress			
		D4	D6	D8	D10
Aloka x IT07K-322-40	08	00	38	63	75
IT07K-322-40 x Aloka	09	22	44	78	89
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-322-40	07	00	43	57	71
IT07K-322-40 x IT03K-378-4	05	00	20	60	80
IT07K-297-13 x IT07K-322-40	09	11	33	44	67
IT07K-322-40 x IT07K-297-13	08	00	00	00	13
IT07K-291-92 x Aloka	08	00	25	50	75
IT03K-378-4 x IT07K-291-92	06	00	00	33	50
IT07K-291-92 x IT03K-378-4	07	29	29	71	86
IT07K-291-92 x IT07K-297-13	08	00	00	00	00

DISCUSSION

This study revealed that different wilting and recovery responses were evident among the newly developed Cowpea genotypes that were evaluated in response to drought stress, they tend to exhibit a wide range of differences starting as early as one week after the final watering, accessions display some phenotypic responses to drought stress which include, senescence, different shades of discolourations, maintenance of stem greenness, cessation of growth and abscission. The finding of this research is in conformity with the earlier study of Maikodomi *et al.* (1999a), who states that among drought response phenotypes assayed in the screened house experiments, maintenance of stem greenness was the only observable feature that was highly compared with both wilting and recovery, as such, this feature provides the only reproducible prediction of drought tolerance or susceptibility. Therefore, based on the result on survival, wilting, recovery and stem greenness, there were significant genotypic differences in performance under drought conditions ($P < 0.05$). Genotypes could be classified into three distinct classes: tolerant, variable, or susceptible. Genotypes Kanannado, Dan-ila, Aloka local, IT07K-378-4, and IT07K-297-13 were consistently tolerant both under wilting and recovery conditions, genotypes IT07K-187-55, IT07K-292-10, IT06K-111, IT07K-293-3, IT07K-299-6, IT07K-298-15, IT07K-243-1-10, IT97K-461-4, IT04K-227-4, IT07K-318-2, IT04K-267-8, and IT97K-568-19 were classified as variable. These genotypes exhibited marked variation in performance both within and between the two conditions. Despite this variability, genotypes tend to perform either on the lower or upper end of the tolerance spectrum. Whereas, IT07K-322-40, IT07K-313-41, IT07K-291-92, IT06K-270, IT07K-244-1-1, and IT06K-275 were susceptible.

According to Singh and Matsui, (2002), in preliminary studies, genotypes which exhibit seedling drought tolerance were more resistant to drought under field conditions than those genotypes which exhibit seedling susceptibility to drought stress. At the phenotypic level, stem greenness was the most reliable screen house-based assayable trait in separating tolerant from susceptible genotypes. The same observation was made in sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L) Moench), where visual scores of greenness were found to be highly correlated with leaf chlorophyll content and drought tolerance. Hsiao and Xu, (2000).

The response of F_1 progenies to drought stress indicates that tolerant progenies were produced when IT07K-322-40 which is a highly susceptible variety was used in both forward and reciprocal crosses except when crossed with IT03K-378-4 which brings about an intermediate tolerance and when crossed with IT07K-297-13, where susceptibility to drought stress is maintained. Aloka local which is a highly tolerant variety showed a promising response of being highly resistant in F_1 progenies when crossed with the two highly susceptible varieties in both forward and reciprocal crosses. Results of this findings also coincide with the work of (Timko *et al.*, 2007a) which says in most cowpea breeding works crosses between susceptible and tolerant/resistant genotypes gives better performance and this is attributed to the possession of the desired traits present in both genotypes. Crosses between IT07K-297-13 and IT07K-322-40 showed the same response in F_1 progeny, where by both in forward and reciprocal crosses the progenies were found to be susceptible to drought stress, this may be due to a certain hybridization problem where the resistance factor was not being properly transferred to the progeny or due to incompatibility. IT07K-291-92, a highly susceptible variety when used as a male stock in the crosses involving Aloka local and IT03K-378-4 both tolerant varieties, produced progenies that were tolerant in the forward crosses except a cross with IT07K-297-13, where susceptibility persisted, as reciprocal crosses were not successful. Crosses between IT07K-297-13 which is a highly drought tolerant with all the two susceptible varieties (IT07K-322-40, and IT07K-291-92) did not reveal any positive response as the resulting F_1 progenies were susceptible to drought stress. These suggest that the resistance factor within the variety was too weak to be transferred and became recessive in all the crosses.

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the performance of developed cowpea genotypes for drought tolerance and it revealed that tolerant Cowpea progenies were produced when IT07K-322-40 which is a highly susceptible variety was used in both forward and reciprocal crosses, this indicates that the gene for drought tolerance is highly heritable in the genotypes of susceptible lines which serves as a base line for researchers to incorporate susceptible lines in their breeding programmes, similarly Kanannado, Dan-ila, and Aloka local which are all local and used as local check, were consistently tolerant both under wilting and recovery conditions.

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